

CALCULATION OF STATISTICAL PARAMETERS OF THE FLOW OF
REQUIREMENTS ARISING IN PLOWING AGGREGATES.

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Abstract: The article covers the issue of analyzing the flow of demand arising in plowing units used in agriculture. During operation, tractors and working machines cause various malfunctions and maintenance requirements. These requirements have the character of a random process, and methods of probability theory and mathematical statistics are used for their analysis. The study examined 169 patients in the Namangan region during 2021-2023. The set of malfunctions noted in the plowing units of the Arion-630s during the autumn plowing season and the requirements for their elimination were studied. As a result, the main statistical parameters of the demand flow - mathematical expectation, variance, coefficient of variation - were determined, and an empirical histogram of the distribution was compiled. Based on the obtained data, the characteristics of the demand flow, subject to the exponential law, are substantiated, and the limits of the confidence interval are calculated. The research results are of practical importance in the effective planning of the maintenance system, determining the optimal location of service centers and repair shops.

Keywords: Plowing units, demand flow, exponential distribution, mathematical expectation, variance, coefficient of variation, service system, confidence interval, Namangan region, Arion-630s tractors.

Plowing units used in agriculture (tractors, trailers, and units assembled with various working machines) require various maintenance and repair requirements during operation. The emergence of these requirements is a random process. Therefore, methods of probability theory and mathematical statistics are used in the analysis of demand flows.

1. The concept of a flow of demand

Demand flow is the sequence of needs for maintenance or repair arising during the operation of units.

It is distributed over time and obeys random laws.

In many cases, an exponential distribution of demand flows is adopted, since demands arise independently and with equal probability.

2. Basic statistical parameters

The following parameters are calculated to represent the flow of requests:

Expected value (\bar{K}) – the arithmetic mean of the flow of incoming requests per unit of time.

$$\bar{K} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^H \dot{K}_j Z_j}{N} \quad (1)$$

Here Z_j – absolute frequency of demands, \dot{K}_j - centers of intervals,

N – absolute frequency.

1. Time between requests (X) - the interval between the arrival of two requests.

If we assume that the flow obeys exponential law, the time intervals are exponentially distributed:

$$f(k_j) = \lambda e^{-\lambda k_j}$$

here: $\lambda > 0$ – distribution parameter (intensity coefficient), e - base of the natural logarithm.

$$\text{Mean value: } \bar{K} = \frac{1}{\lambda},$$

$$\text{Variance: } S_k^2 = \frac{1}{\lambda^2}.$$

2. The variance and coefficient of variation of the number of requests are used to assess the continuity and stability of the flow of requests.

3. Practical significance.

- The effectiveness of the maintenance system is assessed based on statistical data on the flow of requests.
- Determine in which district or farm the greatest demand arises and at what time the need for maintenance of units is highest.
- Based on this, the optimal number and location of service centers and repair shops are determined.

In the article, we will compile a set of numbers representing the flow of orders (requests) submitted to the regional service center by owners of equipment, farms, and agro-clusters in 11 districts to eliminate malfunctions in 169 existing Arion-630s plowing units in the Namangan region during the autumn plowing season of 2021-2023, i.e., a set of total discrete numbers. This collection, which has a random character, is presented in Table 1.

We determine the statistical characteristics of the demand flow in the following order; p. 128.

1. From the set of discrete numbers in Table 1, we select the largest and smallest number of requirements: $K_{\max}=24$, $K_{\min}=1$. Assuming the number of intervals $N=12$, we find the values of the intervals:

$$h = (K_{\max} - K_{\min}) : H = (24 - 1) : 12 \approx 2.$$

2. Determine the values of the interval boundaries K_j and centers and enter them into Table 2 (columns 2 and 3).

3. From the set of numbers, we find the absolute frequencies Z_j of the requirements lying within the constructed 12 intervals. For example, the interval 1 3 corresponds to $Z_j=10$ frequencies. When the frequencies corresponding to each interval are summed, the total absolute frequency is $N=63$ (column 4).

4. We calculate the relative frequency values corresponding to each interval using the formula $P_j=Z_j/N$. For example, for the interval 1 3 $P_j=10/63=0.159$ (column 5). From column 5, it is evident that the sum of the relative frequencies is equal to 1. ($\sum P_j=1,0$).

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5. The arithmetic mean (mathematical expectation) of the flow of requests arising during the season is determined based on the figures of column 6:

Table 1

A set of discrete random numbers representing the flow of demands

24	4	6	24	7	3	21	2	19	14
8	3	18	9	4	3	5	5	6	6
1	10	15	9	6	9	12	10	6	7
13	4	3	6	8	2	9	20	11	6
11	1	9	6	4	13	13	5	22	16
15	9	1	7	4	16	8	8	2	10
5	11	5							

$$\bar{K} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^H \dot{K}_j Z_j}{N} = \frac{534}{63} = 8,47 \frac{\text{demand}}{\text{season}}$$

The average value is the central indicator of the demand flow, without which forecasting, planning, and system analysis are impossible.

Table 2

Demand stream \bar{K} ва S_k^2 Calculation of parameters

T/p	Interval, K_j	Interval Center, \dot{K}_j	Абсолют частота, Z_j	Нисбий частота, $P_j=Z_j/N$	$\dot{K}_j Z_j$	$ \dot{K}_j - \bar{K} $	$(\dot{K}_j - \bar{K})^2$	$Z_j(\dot{K}_j - \bar{K})^2$
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	1÷3	2	10	0,159	20	6,48	41,94	419,41
2	3÷5	4	10	0,159	40	4,48	20,04	200,36
3	5÷7	6	11	0,175	66	2,48	6,13	67,45
4	7÷9	8	10	0,159	80	0,48	0,23	2,27
5	9÷11	10	6	0,095	60	1,52	2,32	13,93
6	11÷13	12	4	0,063	48	3,52	12,42	49,67
7	13÷15	14	3	0,048	42	5,52	30,51	91,54
8	15÷17	16	2	0,032	32	7,52	56,61	113,22
9	17÷19	18	2	0,032	36	9,52	90,70	181,41
10	19÷21	20	2	0,032	40	11,52	132,80	265,60
11	21÷23	22	1	0,016	22	13,52	182,89	182,89

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12	23÷25	24	2	0,032	48	15,52	240,99	481,98
	-	-	N=63,0	1,000	534	82,10	817,58	2069,71

6. The average statistical variance (theoretical variance) is determined by the following formula (column 9):

$$S_K^2 = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^H (K_j - \bar{K})^2 Z_j}{N} = \frac{2069,71}{63} = 32,85 \left(\frac{\text{demand}}{\text{season}} \right)^2.$$

7. The values of the mean square deviation and the coefficient of variation of the discrete random variable K_j are:

$$S_K = \sqrt{S_K^2} = \sqrt{32,85} = 5,73 \frac{\text{demand}}{\text{season}};$$

$$v_k = \frac{S_K}{\bar{K}} = \frac{5,73}{8,47} = 0,676 \approx 0,68$$

8. Using the figures of columns 2 and 4 of Table 2 above, we construct an empirical histogram of the distribution of the K_j demand flow (Fig. 1).

9. The appearance of the histogram allows us to put forward the hypothesis that the flow of demands in plowing units changes according to the law of exponential distribution.

In addition \bar{K} and S_k the proximity of the quantities and $v_k = 0,68$ proves that the random variables change exponentially, since for $\bar{K} = S_k$ and $v_k = 1$ equations are valid [2].

Based on the exponential law, we calculate the single parameter of change - the intensity (density) of the demand flow [2, p. 55].

$$\bar{\lambda} = \frac{1}{\bar{K}} = \frac{1}{8,47} = 0,11 \frac{\text{demand}}{\text{season}}$$

Figure 1. Histogram of the empirical distribution of absolute frequencies (Z_j) of the demand flow K_j

Determination of the limits of the confidence interval of the value of the mathematical expectation of the flow of requests K

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After substantiating the distribution law of random variables K_j , the limits of the confidence interval of the value of the mathematical expectation \bar{K} are determined [2, p. 73].

The confidence interval shows that the value of the mathematical expectation \bar{K} lies within the limits of $K_p \leq \bar{K} \leq K_y$ with probability α (K_p and K_y — \bar{K} are the lower and upper limits of the mathematical expectation).

When the flow of demands changes according to the exponential law K_j , the limit values of the confidence interval are found as follows [2, p. 74]:

$$K_y = r_1 \bar{K} \text{ va } K_p = r_2 \bar{K}$$

where r_1, r_2 are coefficients selected from Table 14 of the literature, depending on the values of the total absolute frequency N and the accepted level of reliability probability α .

Taking $\alpha=0.999$ de6 and considering that $N=63$, we find the values of $r_1=1.18$ and $r_2=0.86$ from Table 14 of the literature [2].

In this case

$$K_y = r_1 \bar{K} = 1,18 \cdot 28,61 = 33,75 \text{ demand/season}$$

$$K_p = r_2 \bar{K} = 0,86 \cdot 28,61 = 24,60 \text{ demand/season}$$

Consequently, that is, the expected value of the flow of demands occurring on tractors during the autumn plowing season lies within the limits of 33.75 and 24.60 with a probability of 0.999 (99%).

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